

ASSOCIATION OF INSULIN RESISTANCE WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

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Article Received on 14 October 2025,

Article Revised on 03 Nov. 2025,

Article Published on 10 Nov. 2025,

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17578073>

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How to cite this Article: Rehana A. R.1, Tauhidul I.2, Zebun Nessa3, Sahida P.4, Ariful H.5, Khaleda H.6, Shahnoor K.7, Muttalib M. A.8, Barua S.9*, Barua R. R.10 (2025). ASSOCIATION OF INSULIN RESISTANCE WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(11), XXX-XXX.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), a reproductive endocrine disorder with quintessential features of metabolic dysfunction, affects millions of women worldwide. Insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia are common findings in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). In insulin-resistant individuals, hyperinsulinemia is a key compensatory mechanism, aimed at maintaining glucose homeostasis. **Objective:** This study was undertaken to determine the association of hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance with nonobese PCOS women. **Methods:** A cross sectional study was conducted in the department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, BIRDEM Academy, Shahbag, Dhaka, from July 2017 to June 2018. According to selection criteria total 83 women of 17 to 36 years of age were selected from the outpatient department of Obstetrics and

Gynecology, BIRDEM-2 General Hospital. Among them 53 were women with established PCOS and 30 were age and BMI matched non PCOS women. In all the subjects, concentrations of fasting plasma glucose, serum insulin, HOMA-IR were estimated. **Results:**

The mean concentrations of serum insulin (30.47 ± 17.01 vs. 13.27 ± 4.80 ; $p < 0.001$) and HOMA-IR (8.41 ± 6.28 vs. 3.22 ± 1.01 ; $p < 0.001$), were significantly increased in women with polycystic ovary syndrome when compared with non PCOS women. Frequency distribution of insulin sensitive and insulin resistant PCOS patients showed 71.7% insulin resistant and 28.3% insulin sensitive. In this study PCOS women were highly associated with insulin resistance than non PCOS women, which was statistically significant (71.7% vs. 13.3%, $\chi^2 = 26.11$, $p < 0.001$). Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that PCOS was independently significant with HOMA-IR. But BMI and waist hip ratio were not significant with HOMA-IR. **Conclusion:** This study concluded that hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance are associated with nonobese PCOS women.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a heterogeneous endocrine disorder that affects 6–10% of women of childbearing age.^[1] In the last 25 years, it has become clear that polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is an important metabolic disorder.^[2] Hyperinsulinemia secondary to a poorly characterized disorder of insulin action is a feature of the polycystic ovary syndrome. Insulin resistance and compensatory hyperinsulinaemia are present in 60–95%^[3] of women with PCOS. Insulin resistance is independent of and exacerbated by obesity.^[4]

Insulin resistance (IR) is typically defined as decreased sensitivity or responsiveness to the metabolic action of insulin.^[5] The pathogenesis of insulin resistance in PCOS remains unclear. Possible mechanism may be functional problems in insulin receptor and defective post receptor signal transduction due to which insulin cannot work to utilize blood glucose.^[6] Also there is significant decrease in number of GLUT4 glucose transporters in PCOS.^[7] As a result blood glucose level increases. Elevated insulin levels are typically described as a compensatory β -cell response to insulin resistance in peripheral tissues.^[8] However these defects can occur in the absence of obesity and glucose intolerance.^[2] Insulin resistance also demonstrates familial aggregation consistent with a genetic trait. Insulin resistance and hyperandrogenemia track together in affected sisters. Genetic analyses have shown evidence of linkage and association of a marker locus on chromosome 19 near the insulin receptor with the hyperandrogenemia phenotype in PCOS families.^[9]

Both lean and obese women with PCOS have increased rates of insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes mellitus compared with BMI matched controls.^[10] Women with PCOS and IR have a significantly increased risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes^[11] and chronic diseases, such as

type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), cardiovascular disease, and metabolic syndrome, which seriously affect the physical and mental health of women of childbearing age, increasing their social burden.^[12] As insulin resistance can be observed several years before the onset of diabetes, an early detection can open the prospect of intervention in order to prevent the disease process.^[13] The homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) is the main method for insulin resistance measurement used in scientific studies because it is simple and noninvasive.^[14]

For many years, insulin resistance was characterized as a consequence of obesity in PCOS patients and not as a primary defect.^[15] But now, insulin resistance has been observed in both normal-weight and obese patients, which contradicts the theory of obesity as the sole driver of insulin resistance.^[16] In the past years many studies have been done around the world on insulin resistance in PCOS women but very limited studies have been done on non obese PCOS women especially in Bangladesh. Since it is an important health problem and a burning issue among the young women, it is a matter of great attention. So, the aim of the study was to determine the association of insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia with non obese PCOS women in Bangladesh. Therefore, women with the disease would be routinely screened for early detection and proper management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, BIRDEM Academy, Dhaka from July 2017 to June 2018. Patients attending in outpatient department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of BIRDEM-2 general hospital were the study population.

According to selection criteria total 83 women of 17 to 36 years of age were selected from outpatient department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of BIRDEM-2 general hospital. Among them 53 were women with established PCOS (Group I) and 30 were age and BMI matched non PCOS women (Group II).

Diagnosed PCOS women aged between 17-36 years were included in this study. Patients with preexisting diabetes mellitus, obesity, Cushing syndrome, thyroid disorder, contraceptive use and other causes of hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance were excluded from the study.

Methods

According to inclusion and exclusion criteria patients were encouraged for voluntary participation in Gynaecological department of BIRDEM -2 Hospital; non PCOS women were also encouraged. When they were agreed for participation, an informed written consent was obtained from them and a structured questionnaire was filled up for each patient. PCOS was diagnosed by the gynaecologist according to Rotterdam criteria. Detail personal, medical, family and socioeconomic histories of study subjects were recorded. Body weight (in kilograms) and height (in meters) of study subjects were measured. Body mass index (BMI) was then calculated as weight (kg)/ height (m²). Waist to Hip Ratio ≥ 0.85 was considered abnormal, < 0.85 was normal.^[17] Based on ACOG criteria: normal-BMI < 25 kg/m², overweight/obese ≥ 25 kg/m².^[18]

Collection and preservation of samples

5 ml venous blood was collected from each study subject after an overnight fasting. From this 5 ml blood sample, 3 ml was delivered in a plain test tube for estimation of serum fasting insulin and 2 ml was delivered in fluoride containing tube for estimation of plasma glucose.

Blood was transported to the laboratory immediately after collection. The serum was separated by removal of clot. Samples were collected in eppendorf tube, labelled properly and stored in freezer at -20°C. Then after 3 months tests were performed.

Fasting plasma glucose was estimated by Glucose Oxidase (GOD-PAP) method. Fasting serum insulin was estimated by Enzyme linked immune sorbent assay (ELISA). Insulin resistance was calculated using HOMA-IR formula:

$$\text{HOMA-IR} = \text{Fasting insulin } (\mu\text{IU/ml}) \times \text{Fasting glucose (mmol/L)} \div 22.5.^{[14]}$$

Normal fasting insulin is 5-25 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$ and HOMA-IR > 2.7 were classified as insulin resistant.^[7]

Data analysis

For comparison of characteristics, mean with standard deviation of fasting glucose, fasting insulin, HOMA-IR were determined. Independent student's t-test was done for comparison between group I and group II. Chi-square test was done to see association of insulin resistance with PCOS. Multiple linear regression analysis was done to find out the relationship of obesity with insulin resistance and PCOS. Statistical analysis was performed

with the help of software SPSS (statistical package for social science) for windows, 17 version. $p < 0.05$ was considered as test of significance.

RESULT

The results of the laboratory investigations i.e. fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA IR of group I and group II are stated in Table I. It was observed that the mean value of fasting glucose (5.94 ± 1.65 vs. 5.51 ± 0.39 ; $p > 0.16$) in both groups were similar but fasting insulin (30.47 ± 17.01 vs. 13.27 ± 4.80 ; $p < 0.001$) and HOMA-IR (8.41 ± 6.28 vs. 3.22 ± 1.01 ; $p < 0.001$) were significantly higher in group I compared to group II (Table I). Figure-1 shows frequency distribution of insulin sensitive and insulin resistant PCOS patients in the study subjects. It is revealed that 71.7% were insulin resistant while 28.3% were insulin sensitive. Table II shows the association of insulin resistance among study subjects in group I and group II. It is revealed that PCOS women were highly associated with insulin resistance than non PCOS women, which was statistically significant (71.7% vs. 13.3%, $\chi^2 = 26.11$, $p < 0.001$). Table III shows multiple linear regression model taking HOMA-IR as a dependant variable in the study. It is revealed that PCOS was independently significant with HOMA-IR. But BMI and waist hip ratio were not significant with HOMA-IR. The women diagnosed as PCOS have on an average 0.62 increased value of HOMA IR than non PCOS women (Table III).

Table I: Comparison of fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA-IR between group I and group II in the study subjects.

Variables	Group I n=53 Mean±SD	Group II n=30 Mean±SD	P-value
Fasting Glucose (mmol/L)	5.94 ±1.65	5.51±0.39	0.16
Fasting Insulin (μIU/ml)	30.47±17.01	13.27±4.80	<0.001
HOMA-IR	8.41±6.28	3.22±1.01	<0.001

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Independent student's t-test was used for statistical analysis. n = number of the subjects, $p > 0.05$ = not significant, $p < 0.001$ = highly significant.

Insulin sensitivity in PCOS patients

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of insulin sensitive and insulin resistant PCOS patients in the study subjects.

Table II: Association of insulin resistance among study subjects in group I and group II.

HOMA-IR	Group I n = 53	Group II n = 30	X ² -value	p-value
HOMA IR ≤ 2.7 (Insulin Sensitive)	15 (28.3)	26 (86.7)	26.11	<0.001
HOMA IR > 2.7 (Insulin Resistant)	38 (71.7)	4 (13.3)		

Statistical analysis was done by Chi-square test to compare among the groups. n= number of the subjects, p<0.001 = highly significant.

Table III: Multiple linear regression model taking HOMA-IR as a dependant variable in the study.

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	p-value	95% Confidence Interval
	B	Std.Error	Beta		
PCOS	0.62	0.10	0.60	<0.001	0.432 to 0.810
BMI (kg/m ²)	0.02	0.02	0.12	0.407	-0.028 to 0.065
Waist hip ratio	0.54	0.77	0.10	0.486	-0.962 to 2.074

p<0.001= highly significant. p>0.05 = not significant.

DISCUSSION

The past decade of research on polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) has produced important new insights into the evaluation and treatment of this disorder. Many studies have been done around the world showing associations of hyperglycemia with PCOS. The association between hyperglycemia and hyperandrogenism was first made by Achard & Thiers (1921) and was called ‘the diabetes of bearded women’. It is now well recognized.^[19] Insulin resistance is an indicator of hyperglycemia which can be detected many years before the onset of hyperglycemia.^[13]

This study was done to determine the association of insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia with non obese PCOS women in Bangladesh. It was a cross sectional study held in the department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, BIRDEM Academy, Dhaka, during the period of July 2017 to June 2018. A total 83 subjects were selected according to the selection criteria. Among them 53 were PCOS women and 30 were non PCOS women. Fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA-IR were estimated and compared statistically to find out the association among the study subjects.

Laboratory findings of fasting insulin showed that women with PCOS had higher levels of fasting insulin (30.47 ± 17.01 vs. 13.27 ± 4.80 ; $p < 0.001$) than non PCOS women. Ahmed M. Mohamadin et al, in their study also found that women with PCOS had significantly higher fasting serum insulin levels compared to healthy controls ($p < 0.05$).^[20] Toprak S et al found that the mean serum insulin level was elevated in lean PCOS patients as compared with control subjects ($p < 0.05$).^[21] Orio et al found that women with PCOS had significantly higher levels of glucose, insulin and HOMA-IR as compared to controls ($p < 0.001$).^[22] But in our study glucose level was normal and there was no significant difference among the study subjects.

In this study the mean value of HOMA-IR (8.41 ± 6.28 vs. 3.22 ± 1.01 ; $p < 0.001$) showed significant difference between group I and group II of the study subjects. This finding was consistent with the findings of Lath et al.,^[19] who in their study found that insulin resistance was higher in patients with PCOS as compared with the controls. In a study of Alebic M.S.^[23] also found PCOS women had higher HOMA-IR than non-PCOS women (controls) even after controlling for BMI and age which is indicative of decreased insulin sensitivity in PCOS and, thus, a higher risk for developing IR-associated metabolic disorders such as impaired glucose tolerance, type 2 diabetes, the metabolic syndrome and potentially cardiovascular disease.^[24] However, hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance occurred in the presence of completely normal glucose level which was similar to study of Alebic M. S.^[23]

In this study it was found that women with PCOS were highly associated with insulin resistance (71.7%) compared to non PCOS women ($p < 0.001$). This is similar to Ambiger et al.,^[7] where prevalence of insulin resistance in PCOS found to be 75%. Similarly a study conducted in India by Kalra et al.,^[25] where insulin resistance was seen in 76.9% among the cases. In another study of El-Mazny et al.,^[26] insulin resistance was found in 29 of the 50 Egyptian women with PCOS, for a prevalence of 58%. Different studies have reported

different prevalence rates of insulin resistance in women with PCOS. This may be due to difference in the ethnicity.^[27] Some investigators have suggested that insulin resistance is universal in these women^[28] whereas others say that it is present in 65% to 70% of cases.^[29] Prevalence of insulin resistance also differs by method used to estimate IR. In a study done by Saxena et al.,^[30] prevalence found to be 88% where they used 2-hour post glucose insulin level to identify IR. However, DeUgarte et al. suggested that the greatest predictive value is characterized by HOMA-IR.^[31] So in this study HOMA-IR was used to calculate insulin resistance.

In this study, using multiple linear regression analysis, PCOS (UC 0.62; SE 0.10; 95 % CI 0.432-0.810) was significant (P<0.001) with HOMA IR independent of BMI and waist hip ratio which are markers of obesity. This finding was consistent with Hoeger,^[32] who found association of insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes with PCOS, even in women with normal body mass index. Similarly Saxena et al.^[30] found that irrespective of weight, PCOS patients (lean as well as overweight or obese), are inherently insulin resistant. Yilmaz et al.,^[33] in their study found that non obese women with PCOS had significantly higher HOMA-IR values than non obese controls.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance is associated with nonobese PCOS women. Convenience sampling method was used and study subjects were limited to patients attending only at the Department of Gynaecology and Obstetrics of BIRDEM-2 General Hospital. Direct relationship and causes of insulin resistance in PCOS could not be explored. Long term multi-centric follow up study of larger and wider range of the population would be ideal. To find out the cause effect relationship of insulin resistance in Bangladeshi women with PCOS, prospective longitudinal study should be done. Study of insulin receptor gene is recommended for further analysis.

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